

PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF JUNIOR SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The article covers the cognitive processes, mental abilities, behavioral norms, and psychological development of junior school students. The methodology for determining the general intellectual levels of children of this age is presented.*

Keywords: *Behavior, education, perception, memory, thinking, attention, imagination, speech, intellectual preparation.*

Introduction: Many changes occur in a child at junior school age. This is a sensitive period for the formation of learning skills, self-management, and the formation of a relationship to knowing the world. The child begins to control his behavior. He clearly understands the norms of behavior about how to behave at home and in public, and can control his emotions in interpersonal relationships with adults and peers. Behavioral norms become his internal requirements, feelings of shyness appear in him. According to psychological literature, the younger school age period includes the period from 6-7 to 10-11 years. The child is prepared for school education in kindergarten. In this, he gets acquainted with the various requirements imposed on students at school, becomes biologically and psychologically ready to learn the basics of science.

Psychological readiness for education means the child's objective and subjective suitability for school requirements. He is first psychologically prepared for school education, therefore, his psyche is sufficiently developed to acquire knowledge, a child of this age is distinguished from children of other ages by the sharpness, clarity, purity, accuracy of perception, his curiosity, generosity, benevolence, trustworthiness, brightness of imagination, strength of memory, clarity of thinking.

In a child preparing for school, attention is relatively long-term and conditionally stable.

The features of a child's attention are manifested in role-playing and plot games, drawing and construction activities, making toys from clay and plasticine, perceiving and understanding the speech of others, solving mathematical operations, listening to and composing stories. The child has a certain level of skill in directing, concentrating, and distributing his attention to a specific object, and strives to control his attention and concentrate it at the right time. His memory is able to accurately remember, retain, and recall interesting, unusual, and surprising information and events. Junior school age includes several stages. Examples of these include:

- Psychological preparation for school education and social conditions of development,
- Adaptation to school,
- Leading activities at the younger school age,

The main psychological innovations at the younger school age. The successful study of a child at school largely depends on their level of school readiness. The child's readiness for school includes the following.

I-Personal preparation. The level of development of the motivational sphere. The presence of interest in knowledge. The desire to occupy a special place in the system of social relations, to perform an important assessed activity, that is, to be a student. II-Intellectual preparation.

The ability to navigate around, the presence of a reserve of knowledge. A certain level of development of perception and visual-figurative thinking. The level of generalization is the ability to distinguish and generalize objects and phenomena. A certain level of development of speech; often, when it comes to mental readiness, the child's worldview, knowledge of living nature, people and their work is understood. This knowledge can be the basis for the education provided by the school, but vocabulary, the ability to perform certain actions cannot be the main indicator of the child's mental readiness for school.

III-Motion readiness; • fine motor skills; • performing large movements (hands, feet, body). IV-Readiness for educational activities; • the ability to listen carefully to adults and accurately follow their instructions; • independently perform the task; • begin to complete the task without paying attention to distracting factors. The main activity of children of primary school age is reading. The child's attendance at school plays an extremely important role in his psychological development and behavior. During this period, the rules of moral behavior are mastered, the social orientation of the personality begins to take shape. The formation of these qualities is associated with the activity of cognitive processes in the child. For example, children of primary school age are distinguished by the sharpness and purity of perception. The main feature of the attention of students of this age is the weakness of will. At this age, the ability to adjust attention by willpower and control it is limited. Due to the relative dominance of the activity of the first signal system in primary school students, visual-figurative memory is more developed in primary school students than in the so-called verbal-logical memory. The imagination of a student of this age is shaped by the influence and requirements of his educational activities. Along with this, direct impressions (visiting museums, sightseeing, watching movies, going on excursions, working on the school grounds, etc.) also develop imagination.

«J. Raven's "Colored Progressive Matrices" methodology is aimed at determining the general level of intelligence of children aged 4.5 to 8 years. The results of our study show that average intelligence (AB) was the highest, i.e. 29.7% in boys and 31.4% in girls. Specific intelligence was 11.6% in boys and 13.5% in girls, and below-average intelligence was 7.7% in boys and 5.9% in girls. This leads to the conclusion that the level of mental development in the studied students is somewhat low due to a number of objective and subjective reasons.

The main reasons for this are the fact that the process of personal development is taking place according to the age, the fact that they have not yet had much time to study at school, and the fact that the environment and necessary measures for the mental development of children in the families where they are raised are not sufficiently established. Based on the above, we would like to note that it is advisable for parents and school teachers to take the necessary measures for the mental development of young students raised in families.

In the study, we tried to study the integral characteristics of the components of creative potential that affect the development of students' creative potential. In this regard, we analyzed the impact of individual psychological (for example, divergent thinking or intelligence), motivational, cognitive activity, creativity, and mental components of the development of creative potential in the process of creative educational activities on the development of creative potential in younger school-age students. Because it is precisely the younger school age period that is an important period in the formation of a child as a comprehensively developed personality in the future. In conclusion, it can be said that for successful education of schoolchildren, it is not necessary to force them, but it is advisable to form motivation in them by organizing games, dramatic lessons, and demonstration lessons, according to the characteristics of their age.

The formation of positive educational motivation of younger schoolchildren is of great importance, which has a positive impact on the development of the creative potential of each child, as one of the tasks of the teacher - to manage the creative activity of younger schoolchildren, that is, to strengthen their enthusiasm for learning, knowledge, self-confidence, and develop their internal natural strengths and abilities by forming their constant motivation for purposeful learning. At the same time, it is important for students to work together on the basis of verbal-communicative, instrumental-manipulative and graphic means.

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